

Explicit Strategy Training and Learner Autonomy

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ABSTRACT

As an elusive but important term in language teaching, learner autonomy, along with the possible ways of its enhancement, is coming to the forefront in Asian EFL context. This study investigated the possibility that there might be an impact of explicit strategy training on Iranian intermediate EFL learner autonomy and language proficiency. To come to conclusion, two groups each with 25 intermediate learners served as the experimental and control group. In the experimental group, explicit strategy training was practiced. ALQ questionnaire was used as the measure of learners' autonomy and PET was used as the measure of proficiency. The results of the study show that learners' autonomy increases as the effect of explicit strategy training. Explicit strategy training can also affect the learners' proficiency in general.

KEYWORDS: learner autonomy, explicit strategy training, language proficiency

1.1. INTRODUCTION

Since its introduction, the autonomy approach has been shifting the foci of language classrooms from teacher-centered to student-centered and from teaching-centered to learning-centered (Holec, 1985). Learner autonomy is mostly seen as a significant educational goal, and the link between learner autonomy and effective learning has led to various pedagogical attempts in a wide variety of contexts to foster learner autonomy. (Jones, 1995; Aoki & Smith, 1999).

With its promising tenets, autonomy seems to have become a significant part of the current orthodoxy of language teaching and learning research and practice. The publication of Rubin (1975) and Stern (1975) brought the research on learner strategy into the forefront, causing a tendency toward finding the good language learners strategies. The question for course designers is how these various characteristics, skills, and strategies of good language learners can be supported. To Little (1995) increasing awareness of strategies although doesn't guarantee learners applying them but providing guided opportunities for their use helps learners to achieve the confidence necessary to learn the language autonomously. So training is needed to help students become aware of useful approaches and strategies, and modify attitudes about learning (Bown, 2006; Thang, 2005; White, 2003).

As the approach of strategy training found its advocates, new models of strategy training such as O'malley and Chamot (1990) and Harris (2003) emerged. Common to all the models was a four step procedure beginning from a scaffolded help of the teacher to the point that learners can use the strategies independently (Chamot et al, 1990):

1. Raising awareness of the strategies learners already using;
2. Teacher presentation and modeling of strategies so that students become increasingly aware of their own learning and thinking processes;
3. Multiple practice opportunities to help students move toward autonomous use of strategies through gradual withdrawal of the scaffolding
4. Self- evaluation of the effectiveness of strategies used and transfer of strategies to fresh tasks,

LLS research has shown that students often do not automatically transfer the strategies they learn in one context to a different situation (O'Malley & Chamot, 1990; Davidson & Sternberg, 1998). Teachers assist in strategy transfer in two ways: first by developing students' metacognition through explicit strategy instruction and second, by discussing with students how they might apply a strategy in a different context.

The current research is an attempt to examine the merits of practicing learner autonomy in Iranian EFL context within which the traditional attitude hold by teachers and learners towards their very own roles seem to be barrier to self-access and independency on the part of the language learner, so the research aims at finding out whether explicit strategy training can affect learners autonomy on one hand and language proficiency on the other.

2.2. Research Questions and Hypothesis

1. Does explicit strategy training improve learners' autonomy?
2. Does explicit strategy training improve learners' English language proficiency?

3.1. METHODOLOGY

The participants were 50 both male and female adult English learners all intermediate studying English in 2 classes. In one, explicit strategy was practiced and the other class served as the control group. None of the candidates knew that they were part of a research project so there was a kind of randomization to ensure the validity of the results.

The students' proficiency was measured using PET to collect the data on the students proficiency test, the Persian version of Autonomy Learner Questionnaire was administered in class prior to the study as a pre-test and after the implementation period at the end of the twelfth week as a post-test.

The Autonomy Learner Questionnaire was formed by Egel in 2003 who reports the reliability of the questionnaire to be about .80 using the Cronbach Alpha. The questionnaire includes 44 statements based on nine dimensions related to language learning. The items in these dimensions depict whether learners display a greater degree of control in particular aspects of their learning. Table.1 below displays the nine areas for investigation in the autonomy learner questionnaire.

To ensure that the groups are not significantly different in terms of autonomy, the ALQ was administered as a pretest for autonomy to both groups and the data obtained were analyzed using independent t-test (table.2). The results show that there is no significant difference between the groups (.812>.05)

Table.1: Nine Dimensions in the Autonomy Learner Questionnaire

Section	Number of items	Focus	Questions
Dimension 1	6 items	Readiness for Self-direction	What are the learners' beliefs relating to self-directed learning in general?
Dimension 2	7 items	Independent Work in Language Learning	What are the learners' beliefs relating to independent work in language learning?
Dimension 3	8 items	Importance of Class/ Teacher	How important do learners see the class/ the teacher in their language learning?
Dimension 4	5 items	Role of Teacher: Explanation/ Supervision	What importance do learners give to teacher explanation and supervision?
Dimension 5	4 items	Language Learning Activities	In relation to particular language learning activities, what are the learners' attitudes?
Dimension 6	3 items	Selection of Content	What are the learners' attitudes relating to the selection of content for language learning?
Dimension 7	2 items	Objectives/ Evaluation	How confident do learners feel about defining objectives?
Dimension 8	5 items	Assessment/ Motivation	How important is external assessment in motivating the learners' work?
Dimension 9	4 items	Other Cultures	What are the learners' attitudes relating to the culture of other countries?

(Egel, 2003)

At the end of the course, the same autonomy questionnaires were given to the students to determine the possible changes. The same version of PET test was used to find any significant difference between the classes which have practiced different dimensions to autonomy and the control one.

Table: 2. statistics for ALQ as a pretest.

VAR00002	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
VAR00001	Control	25	111.60	11.95		
	EST	25	110.80	11.50	.239	48 .812

Different dimensions of the autonomy questionnaire used in the study were analyzed using t-test. The mean of post-test PET tests were compared using t-test to determine any significant difference between the groups in terms of proficiency.

4.2. Results and Discussion of Autonomy Learner Questionnaire

ALQ the Likert scale (Likert,1932) was employed by asking the participants to respond to a total of 44 statements by indicating whether each statement is "always true", "mostly true", "sometimes true", "rarely true", and "never true" for themselves. The items in the ALQ were based on independency and dependency; therefore a reverse scoring system was necessary for the independent items in order to discriminate between attitudes of autonomous learners and those of non-autonomous learners.

4.2.1. Statistical Data Analysis of Autonomy Learner Questionnaire Dimensions

The ALQ was administered to the group before and after the treatment span. To find out whether the participants' learner autonomy was fostered, an independent samples t-test was run so that the mean value of the post-test in each dimension of the ALQ in the control group could be compared to the mean value of those of the experimental group in the post-test. The post test mean scores of each dimension in each group were compared and the results are presented below.

The first dimension—Readiness for Self-Direction—concerns with readiness to engage in self-directed learning in general. The dimension has six items, all based on learner independency, aiming to investigate to what extent the students are ready to participate in self-directed activities of English learning. Table 3. indicates that there is a difference in the extent the students in groups are ready to participate in self-directed activities when learning English after the implementation period.

The second dimension covers the students' general attitudes to independent learning. In other words, these seven items investigate if the students are able to learn English on their own without the help of a teacher. As observed in Table 3, there seems to be an impact of explicit strategy training on independent work of language learners as one aspect of autonomy.

Table. 3: Statistics for Dimensions of ALQ

dimensions		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
D1	control	25	20.16	2.37			
	EST	25	21.92	2.69	2.45	48	.018
D2	control	25	18.32	1.81			
	EST	25	20.20	1.91	3.55	48	.001
D3	control	25	21.24	2.58			
	EST	25	23.60	2.73	3.13	48	.003
D4	control	25	14.40	1.75	6.72	48	.000
	EST	25	17.88	1.90			
D5	Control	25	09.08	2.08	.341	48	.735
	EST	25	09.28	2.07			
D6	control	25	07.40	1.52	.603	48	.549
	EST	25	07.68	1.74			
D7	control	25	05.40	1.82	5.57	48	.000
	EST	25	07.88	1.26			
D8	control	25	13.68	2.10	2.05	48	.045
	EST	25	14.84	1.88			
D9	control	25	09.20	2.06	1.74	48	.088
	EST	25	10.32	2.46			

The third dimension of the questionnaire aims to discover the learners' evaluation of the importance of the role of the classroom and the teacher. The dimension has got eight items. Five of these items are based on the attitudes of no autonomous learners that the teacher plays a very important role in learning a foreign language, whereas the other three items are based on the learner independency. In this dimension, reverse scoring was conducted. Accordingly, the higher score they get, the less important they regard the classroom and the teacher. Table.3 shows the enhancement in the students' independency in learning English

The fourth section of the questionnaire evaluates the importance of the role of the teacher as in the third dimension. Table.3 highlights that students have become less dependent on the teacher. As cited in Egel (2003, p. 102), the items in this dimension examines beliefs on working co-operatively, working outside of the classroom, and independent learning in specific areas such as the receptive skills. The first two are accepted as having independent qualities. As it is shown in Table 3 the learners willingness in joining the classroom activities and extending their language studies outside the classroom setting doesn't show a rising tendency in the EST group.

The items in sixth dimension of the ALQ deal with the students' tendency toward sharing the responsibility to select the content and materials for their English lesson. As indicated in table.3 show that explicit strategy training can not affect the learners' autonomy regarding the students' tendency toward choosing the content.

Dimension seven constitutes two items investigating the students' *intrinsic motivation* for language learning. Table 3 implies the explicit strategy training can positively affect the learners' extrinsic motivation. The items in this section are concerned with the learners' attitudes towards external assessment and its role in motivating them. Of the five items, number thirty-nine shows independency and the others dependency of the language learners. T-test results in table 3 shows that the external assessment becomes less important in motivating the learners' work.

The eighth dimension with five questions deals with assessment and how it can motivate learning a foreign language. The data collected, show a difference between the control and experimental group.

The four items in the ninth dimension aim to investigate the learners' attitudes toward the culture of other countries. As the table shows the attitude of the learners in the experimental group don't show any increase

4.3. ALQ- Independency Levels

The Autonomy Learner Questionnaire used in this study aims to survey to

What extent the students' behaviors can be autonomous. Accordingly, it was favorable that the experimental group has higher scores which may show a stronger orientation toward autonomy after the twelve weeks implementation span. In this section, the independency levels of the participants will be analyzed. This will be done by considering the scores gained by each of the participants depending on the chart of ALQ scores which determine the degrees of learner independency as follows; 0-44 = More Dependent, 45-88 = Dependent, 89-132 = Neutral, 133-176 = Independent and 177- 220 = More Independent .

Table.4: Statistics for ALQ- Independency Levels

VAR00002	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
VAR00001	Control	25	118.88	12.18			
	EST	25	133.52	12.00	4.279	48	.000

As shown in table 4, the EST group has reached the mean of 133.25 which is assumed to be an indication of the independency of the learners in the group as compared to the mean of the control group which is 118.88. Also the significance of .000 which is less than the alpha decision level (.05) is an indication of the significant difference between the groups as a whole.

4.4. Results and Discussion of PET as the Proficiency Test

Since the study was an investigation of the impact of the explicit strategy training both on learner autonomy and general proficiency, the same version of PET was also used as the post test to find out whether practicing explicit strategy training has any impact on the proficiency of language learners.

Table 5. Statistics for PET as the post test

VAR00002	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
VAR00001	control	25	65.64	5.40			
	EST	25	69.04	5.53	2.197	48	.033

Based on what is depicted in table.5 it can be concluded that practicing explicit strategy training has positive impacts on language proficiency.

5. Conclusion

As Gremmo observes (1995:151), the last 25 years have seen an increasing amount of attention to learner autonomy through a focus on learner reflection and taking responsibility for one's own learning processes, self-directed learning, self-access systems and individualized/independent learning in second language learning literature.

The current research tries to investigate a way to improve learner autonomy in an Asian context which is assumed to be a teacher-centered one. Explicit strategy training was practiced as a way to develop learner autonomy. The results indicate that practicing explicit strategy training can enhance learner autonomy in general and in all dimensions except dimensions five, six and nine. It also helped the learners to improve their proficiency. The fact that it develops some of the dimensions and not all, however, calls for a more comprehensive approach to develop autonomy. It should be also kept in mind that the study was done in an Asian context in which the shift of foci from teacher to learner and from teaching to learning would take a lot of time and energy, and results of the study sound promising.

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